

INFLUENCE OF GRAPHITIZATION PROCESSING UPON THE CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITE INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES

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SUMMARY: The ultimate properties of carbon-carbon (CC) composite are determined by its processing history and interfacial structure to a great extent [1,2]. As the complexity of manufacture and the difficulty to control it, The CC composite's quality varies with the fluctuation of processing condition intensely. Thus, it is essential to optimize the processing to increase and stabilize its quality by monitoring the interfacial properties during manufacture. In this paper, the author investigates the inter-bundle and outer-bundle interfacial bond strength of three dimensional woven and pierced CC composite after each graphitization treatment cycle. Results show that the inter-bundle interface has nearly reached the highest bond strength after four graphitization treatment cycles, while the outer-bundle interface does not display best interfacial performance until six graphitization treatment cycles.

KEY WORDS: carbon-carbon composites, interfacial micro-mechanical properties, push out test method, three dimensional woven structure

INTRODUCTION

Carbon-carbon material is one of the important advanced composites with many excellent properties. It does not only occupy outstanding ablation resistance, remarkable high temperature resistance and low density property(theory density is 2.2g/cm³), but also displays best wear-resisting property and dimensional stability. CC composite has been used from the primitive aero-space field such as wing leading edge, nose cap and rocket generator sprayer nozzle, etc. to transport, sport and medical fields to day [3,4]. There is evidence to belief that in the near future, the CC composite will play a more important role in a widespread range. However, two problems limit its further using now. The first case is the high cost of production, another is the fluctuation of properties. In some special field, the cost may be unimportant, but fluctuation of quality is always a fatal problem that prevents its development. One of the important reason is that the random variation in manufacture. Generally, CC processing includes five to six cycles of impregnating with resin, carbonization and graphitization treatments. Too many parameters and too long producing period result in difficulty to control the processing in uniform condition. Up to now, many researchers have engaged in studying on CC composite, and their fields can be summarized into four aspects:

1. Investigating physical structure and chemical composition in matrix and interface by scanning electron microscope(SEM), transmission electron microscope(TEM), scanning tunnel microscope (STM) and atomic force microscope(AFM), etc.[5,6,7,8].
2. Designing new weaving method and program using CAD & CAM techniques [9].
3. Analyzing mechanical performance and fracture properties through mathematics model and mechanical theory [8,10].
4. Characterizing mechanical, ablation and thermal properties, etc. based on experimental techniques [11]

Although the focus of the four aspects is much different, each of them has realized the importance of interface in CC material. The structure condition of interface directly influences CC composite's mechanical properties. And in further, it can effect on ablation resistance as well. With perfect interfacial bond state, the CC material generally appears excellent behavior of resisting airstream washing, heat shock and shear and prevents the big piece of carbon matrix peeled off composite block during ablation condition. Well, it does not mean that the stronger the interface bond strength is, the better the properties of CC composite are. For CC composite, both the fiber and matrix is brittle material that too stronger interfacial bond state can induce to brittle fracture.

In addition, during the tension test on 3-D woven CC composite, many fiber bundles are pulled out when fracture is happened and while the higher tension strength always obtained correspondingly(Fig.1). It implies that there is a new type of interfacial structure in woven CC composite besides the conventional interface that exists between the single fiber and matrix. In fact, the newer is a type of macro-interface that is between one bundle of carbon fibers and the surrounding matrix. For sake of distinguishing, the macro-interface can be termed as outer-bundle interface and the conventional can be termed as inter-bundle interface(Fig.2). The whole properties of CC composite are determined by the cooperation of them. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the different bond strength of them in different CC specimens using push-out test method. During the test, a load-displacement curve is recorded, and from the curve and through simple calculation, the interfacial shear strength can be obtained.

Fig.1: Tension fracture picture of 3-D CC

Fig 2: Interface in 3-D CC

EXPERIMENT

Specimens Preparation

The experimental material is three dimensional woven pierced carbon-carbon composite made from PAN based carbon fiber and coal pitch. First, the fiber preform impregnated with pitch under 8 atm., and then impregnated under 10 atm.. The material is treated by impregnation, carbonization and graphitization for six times in total. After each cycle, a piece of specimen is cut off the block for test.

Test Instrument

The interfacial bond force is characterized by a modified push-out instrument, its diagram and the test technique are shown in Fig.3 and 4.

1-CCD camera, 2- microscope, 3-XY translation stage, 4-load and displacement cells, 5-sample, 6-loading device, 7-data acquisition system

Fig. 3 Illustration of equipment used for carbon-carbon composites push-out test

Fig. 4 Schematic illustration of push-out test

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Load-Displacement Curve of Push-Out

Fig. 5 gives out the SEM photographs of inter-bundle and outer-bundle interface after push-out test. In Fig. 6-7 the displacement is the relative displacement between probe tip and specimen surface. The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) is evaluated from the follows equation.

$$\tau = P/pdL \tag{1}$$

Fig. 5 the SEM picture of the push-out specimens

Fig.6 Inter-bundle interface push-out curve

Fig.7 Outer-bundle interface push-out curve

The curves show that the push out procedures of fiber and fiber bundle are both divided into two stages. The first is interfacial debonding stage as indicated in the curves from P0 to Pd section. In this sequence, with the increase in displacement the load linearly increases until reaches the interfacial critical bonding strength, and then appears a sudden drop. The load on the moment is regarded as the maximum bond force of interface. Subsequently, the frictional sliding stage starts that fiber or fiber bundle is gradually pushed out of the matrix. But in Fig.6

the single fiber sliding stage is not distinct that the load continues to increase immediately after a small drop happened, which is because that the diamond probe tip comes into contact with the surrounding matrix surface after the fiber's axial movement (Fig.4). Whereas, in the case of fiber bundle(Fig.7), the sliding procedure is distinctly visible. Sometimes, the maximum frictional stress even surpasses the maximum bond stress(P_d) due to the roughness of debonding fiber bundle surface.

Besides, from the bundle push-out curve it can be seen that there is a small stress peak(P_x) appeared before the maximum stress(P_d) reaches. Although the small peak is not always appeared in test, its existing implies that the debonding process of fiber bundle does not happened at one time, partial debonding or inter-bundle debonding may occur before the complete debonding happens. It induces to more difficulty to analyze the failure mechanism of outer-bundle interface.

Effect of Graphitization Treatment Processing on Interfacial Strength

The specimens are divided into six groups signed as 1G#, 2G#, 3G#, 4G#, 5G#, 6G#, which expresses the different graphitization treatment times respectively. The shear strength values of inter-bundle and outer-bundle interfaces are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: The shear strength of inter-bundle and outer-bundle interfaces in different graphitization treatment

In Fig. 8, the treatment temperature of graphitization is basically similar except for the fourth cycle (2800°C) And it is shown that the two kinds of interfacial strength values have similar increase tendency with the increase in graphitization times before the fourth graphitization treatment. Whereas, after the fourth cycle, they display quite different tendency that while the inter-bundle interfacial shear strength changes to monotonically decreases, the outer-bundle interfacial shear strength continues to monotonically increase after a small drop. The reason is that the formation speeds of two kinds of interface are not equal. In other words, the matrix in the fiber bundle reaches the densified structure after the fourth cycle, and expresses high interfacial shear strength. The subsequent graphitization treatment has few effects on the densification of matrix. On the contrary, it can induce to further crystallization and

contraction of volume in matrix, which results in additional stress produced in interface and decrease of inter-bundle interfacial shear strength. At the same condition, matrices between the bundles need six cycles to reach more densified structure at least. Thus, in the whole treatment procedure the shear strength of outer-bundle interface continues to increase except for the drop that caused by temperature case.

The above phenomenon is directly related with the woven structure of CC material. In the fiber preform, fibers in the bundles are closed together while between the bundles are spaced apart. If the preform is impregnated with pitch, more pitch will fill between bundles and when the pitch is heated and sintered into carbon, big bubbles will be generated between the fiber bundles as more pitch and space exists. When the pressure in bubbles gradually increases to the critical degree, the bubbles will break into many small drops and squeeze in fiber bundles, while the resin in bundles can not generate big bubbles for the restriction of surrounding fibers and it sinters into carbon in-situ. In Fig. 8, the shear strength drop of outer-bundle interface at the fourth cycle reveals the same reason that the loose matrix and interface structure at the fourth cycle between fiber bundles is easy to produce cracks under the high treatment temperature, but in the densified fiber bundles that can not appear.

From the discussion above, clearly the adjustment of process can induce to different interfacial structure. This may provide useful information for material design.

CONCLUSION

There are two kinds of interface in multidimensional woven carbon-carbon composites that one kind is inter-bundle interface, another is outer-bundle interface. Their performance speeds during the manufacture procedure are not equal. The push-out test results show that before the fourth graphitization cycle, matrix in fiber bundles is densified faster than that out of bundles at same condition. That is to say, the inter-bundle interfacial strength increases more quickly than outer-bundle interfacial strength. The high graphitization treatment in the fourth cycle effects the outer-bundle interface more obviously than inter-bundle interface as the different densities of them.

REFERENCES

1. Schmid, T. E., AFWAL-TR-82-4159, 1982.
2. Scott, R. D, NASA CR 1658421-1, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Washington, DC, 1982.
3. Carroll, T. J. and Connors, D. F. "Final Report for Rapid Densification of 2D Carbon-Carbon Preforms", Textron Specialty Materials Report, Dec. 1989.
4. Curry, Donald M., "Carbon-Carbon Materials Development and Flight Certification Experience From Space Shuttle", Oxidation-Resistant Carbon Carbon Composites for Hypersonic Vehicle Application. NASA CP-2051, 1988, pp. 29-50.
5. Dhimi, T. L., Bahl, O. P. and Manocha, L. M. "Influence of Matrix Precursor on the Oxidation Behavior of Carbon-Carbon Composites", Carbon, Vol. 31, No. 5, 1993, pp.751-756.

6. Rellick, G. S. and Adams, P. M., "TEM Studies of Resin-Based Matrix Microstructure in Carbon/Carbon Composites", *Carbon*, Vol. 32, No. 1, 1994, pp. 127-144.
7. Huang, H. and Young, R. J. "Effect of Fiber Microstructure Upon the Modulus of PAN- and Pitch-Based Carbon Fibers", *Carbon*, Vol. 33, No. 2, 1995, pp. 97-107.
8. Kowbel, W. and Shan C. H. "Mechanical Behavior of Carbon-Carbon Composites Made with Cold Plasma Treated Carbon Fibers", *Composites*, Vol. 26, No. 11, 1995, pp. 791-797.
9. Emmerich, F. G. "Application of a Cross-Linking Model to the Young's Modulus of Graphitizable and Non-Graphitizable Carbons", *Carbon*, Vol.33, No.1, 1995, pp. 47-50.
10. Emmerich, F. G. and Luengo, C. A., "Young's Modulus of Heat-Treated", *Carbon* , Vol. 31, No. 2, 1993, pp. 333-339.
11. Anand, K. and Gupta, V. "the Effect of Processing Conditions on the Compressive and Shear Strength of 2-D Carbon-Carbon Laminates", *Carbon*, Vol. 33, No. 6, 1995, pp. 739-748.